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South-western tribes of Odisha : A Socioeconomic analysis

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ABSTRACT

Odisha is a tribal-dominated state. Since ancient times, many tribes have been living in its forests as tribes. Looking at the population ratio, it is known that about 23 percent of the total population in our state is tribal. Means, South-western part of odisha (kalahandi, koraput, rayagada, malkangiri) is located by approximately 45 percent tribes of the state tribal population. Therefore, although they constitute a large part of our population, the government has tried to provide them with real development, but it is not easily possible. They are living a neglected and dark life in inaccessible, remote areas without roads. But day by day, the government is paying close attention to their development. Various schemes are being implemented for their development. Roads are being built to access the forest areas that are an obstacle to their progress. Special attention is being given to their education, health and other advancements through blocks, tehsils. Here my study will be focus on their economic structure and social life.

Keywords: *Affluent, PVTGS, MNP, Conservation, Product, Indigenous, Implement, Merchant, Policy, Scheme, Provide, Trade, Selling, Market*

INTRODUCTION :

There are 62 tribal groups in the state. Out of which 13 are primitive tribal groups, 9 primitive tribal group or PVTGs are living in south-western area (kalahandi, koraput, rayagada and malkangiri). Some of the prominent tribal communities are - Kandha, Dal, Gadba, Gand, Didai, Parja, Banda, Banjara, Munda, Shabar, Kutia, Dongari, Khadia, Soura, Bida, Bhumija, Amanatya, Bhuyan, Lodha, Ho, etc. They mostly live in the tribal-dominated districts of Odisha, namely Koraput, Rayagada, Malkangiri, Nabarangpur, Kalahandi, Sundargarh, Ganjam, Gajapati, Keonjhar, Mayurbhanj, Balangir, Phulbani, Angul, Nuapada, Bargarh etc. The largest number of them, namely - about 21 types of tribal live only in the undivided Koraput

district. Therefore, Koraput is a tribal-dominated district of Odisha.

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Tribes are living in very remote areas and top of the hills, mountains and forests. These are further divided into two groups. Namely-

- (1) Pratna munda Tribe: Korenga, Juanga Gadiya, Santali,
- (2) Pratna Dravidian Tribe: Mundari, Bhumija, Parja, Kutia, Dangaria, Khand , Bonda, Didayi, Gond, Banjara etc.

Pratna Dravidian Tribes are found in Odisha. Meanwhile, the most affluent tribal settle in South-Western part of Odisha, especially in the districts of Koraput, Rayagada, Malkangiri and Kalahandi.

DISCUSSION :

The Kandha tribe is the most in terms of numerical superiority, while the bonda is the less numerous among these groups. Their economic development is very low. Since they have no land, they burn the forests and cultivate. They cut the forest and sow seeds of various crops. It has been said earlier that they earn money by collecting minor forest products from the forest and selling them in the market. Apart from this, they collect wood and leaves and sell them. This sale does not yield the expected profit. There is no work done. Apart from this, they collect and sell the leaves of the forest.

Currently, the Central Government has a project plan to provide flood protection in the forest areas. But the implementation has been stopped till date. The Central Government in October 25/1980, when Forest Conservation has done and the tribal who were in possession of the land were protesting for the provision of land. It was unsuccessful. A bill in this regard was introduced by the Government of India in Lok Sabha 2005. Its name is Schedule Tribe (Re-organization of Forest Rights) Bill; the bill includes how to help tribal living in forest areas if they are displaced. There is a proposal to provide a maximum of two and a half acres of land per tribal family. But that has not been implemented yet. During elections, political parties sometimes promise this to the tribal. But no action is taken.

ECONOMY STRUCTURE :

They earn money by selling of minor forest product. The yield of this crop is not sufficient. Their agricultural activities include various stages of festivals such as sowing seeds, sowing seedlings, planting rice plants, getting pregnant with rice flowers, harvesting rice and many more. South-western part of odisha's tribal family is a communal family. Even if it is just for food and drink, they need money for their daily needs, housing, etc. In the areas near malkangiri district, koraput district, Niamgiri, Perumunji, Lanjgarh areas in Kalahandi district. In these area's tribal included in the Karlapat sanctuary of kalahandi, Minajhola, Gumma, chatikona range of Rayagada district, laxmpur, Balda Cave m deomali range of koraput district , chitrakunda of malkangiri district pulses like- kolath, maandia, baajra, kaandul, katting, beerli, jhudung are mainly produced.

Under the influence of modernity, they have adopted rice as their staple food, but it is not sufficient. They selling products in the market at a low price, but when others bring some from them to the market, it is sold at double the price. As a result, the tribe are getting less profit in the form of money, while the traders and middlemen are getting more money.

Therefore, the government should make arrangements for business. They can get actual profit from their product. Paddy, Maandia, Gurji are their main food. The Mandia Rani festival is celebrated. It is also celebrated by other groups and caste in south-western Odisha. In morden term is the Nuakhai festival. it was started by the tribal firstly, there is no doubt about it. Earlier they did not pay attention to food and dress. But after coming in contact with the people of the modern era, they have led a new life. Due to the impact of this modernity, their expenses have increased. But on the other hand, their income is not that much.

However, the agricultural system has improved with their indigenious technology. They do not get agricultural schemes properly from the government. They have been collecting forest produce and growing some vegetables for their household expenses. Due to this vegetable farming, the economy has improved very slowly.

In addition, although they are unfamiliar with modern farming methods, they are using their own equipment and collecting food using various techniques. Now, with the improvement of their life, the form of money is being affected in many ways. For this, some people have learned to work as daily wage labourer to earn money, there is a shortage of money because they have no income, and they only get money from the things collected from the forest and from the pluses. Their expenses are more than their income.

As a result, that is why they are still the same as they were before. In this way, the negative impact is inevitable in any region; the lifestyle of this area's tribe is regulated by the natural structure and environmental conditions. In Kalahandi, koraput, malkangiri and Rayagada' approximately 50 percent of the land is mountainous. Of this, half of the land is not suitable for agriculture. In the plains, the farmers improve their economic misery to some extent by producing Rabi crops. The land of the tribal Sarvaswa groups is unsuitable for agriculture. They mainly depend on the forest for 8/9 months of the year. The mahul tree, the turnip tree and Salap tree are identified as their specific personal assets.

They get some money from the alcohol prepared from it. One makes a living by making mahul and rice wine all year round. Similarly, alcohol is prepared from the salap tree. One makes 5/6 months from the money earned by making alcohol from the salap tree. When the salap tree dies, it is cut down, the seeds are taken out, dried and rolled into a mat and made into cakes and cakes. During the rainy season, they take out many types of roots, dry that in the sun, roll them in a mat, make cakes and eat that. Similarly, mango takua and kasla kanda are also the means of their economy.

The Rayagada tribal of Lanjigarh earn money by harvesting mangoes, bananas, oranges, plantains, turmeric, mustard etc. They burn the forest and harvest the first year's harvest of kandul, seed, beeri etc. in the second year mustard, kangu, kasla and in the third year, when the land becomes fertile, they harvest paddy. In this way, the production of the tribes, fruits and hunting etc. continues. Traders or merchants go to the houses of

the tribal to buy forest products at a low price and sell them at a higher price in the plains. Therefore, the economic pressure on their livelihood is particularly high.

HEALTH AND POLICIES -:

During the British rule, missionary doctors used to provide medicine for diseases in tribal area's and free of cost. The tribal of this land faced still drink water suffering. There are no tube wells or ponds. Due to contaminated drinking water and food, various deadly diseases are spreading. For this, various steps were taken, and the tribal around that hill have started observing fasts from there. Since they are not allowed to go there, when doctors are denied, they believe in Gunigaredi Mannatantra Dai, Chiriguni etc. and observe fasts from government medical treatment. Although efforts were made to provide modern treatment to these tribal, it has not been possible.

Child mortality, malaria, cholera, worms, and obesity are particularly common among the tribal of Kalahandi and undivided koraput.

Therefore, a hospital should be established in the place where they are settled and it is only right to provide medicine free of cost. Their population is decreasing compared to other castes. Research has shown that the government has made arrangements for them in agriculture, cooperative animal husbandry, education, industry. Irrigation, women and they have provided education system and road construction system for children. But none of them have been implemented yet. If all those systems are implemented, their education and economic livelihood will be improved.

It is proof that the government is spending on tribal. But on the other hand, when we come to them, it is empty. Therefore, the government should adopt a proper method to implement. As long as the tribes of south-western part of odisha the rural or deep forests continue to suffer. India will be considered an Under Developed area for the KBK (undivided koraput) project; the Central Government gave Rs. 250 crore as Special Central Assistance to various departments in many times.

Another, newly implemented project is the 'Tribal Employment and Livelihood Programme'. It was launched in the state on October 7, 2004. Its objective is to improve the living conditions of the tribal in the interior areas, which is maximum cover particular these areas. The project was implemented in 30 blocks of 7 districts at a cost of about Rs. 403 crore for 10 years, but the tribals of Kalahandi, koraput, malkangiri and rayagada have not got a profit it. A bill was introduced stating that more than Rs. 30 crore was spent on the IFAD block among IFAD, DFID, WEP organizations. But the results were not encouraging.

There is a complete welfare department for the tribal. But if those measures were implemented properly, then with their progress, India's development would have progressed as a prerequisite. Its responsibility is assigned to all Welfare Officer like ADWO, DWO subdivision at the district level and a WO at the block level.

As per the recommendations of some committees, special arrangements should be made for the tribal villages, which are regulated for their protection (Regulation 2 of 1956) which is essential for implementation. Capitalists, traders and owners are taking the lands of the tribal in their own names and treat them as a labour. On the other hand, others take away their collected goods at a lower price. The government should make a special plan for them to buy the goods. As a result, the tribal directly benefited. The tribal group is mostly illiterate. There is no road to reach their villages. It was observed that out of the 8 villages in the block we visited and researched, only one school was there. It is unimaginable that they have remained, when education has spread in the country. They are still wandering in the dark world.

Today's, their economy has improved somewhat compared to the previous 10 years, along with the spread of education. The education system has become disconnected from their life. In 2003-04, Rs. 3 lakh was given for Pre Matric & Post Matric respectively. It does not seem that any tribal students have benefited from this.

CONCLUSION:-

Due to poverty, it has become difficult to study. Before acquiring education, one needs a livelihood. Therefore, they have to sacrifice their entire life in search of food. It seems essential to take steps for the development of education by taking steps for livelihood first. They are the exact copy of primitive man. Earlier, man lived in dense forests. Similarly, today, he is losing himself in the sound of the gurgling stream and the rustling of the trees. Makangiri, Rayagda, Koraput, Kalahandi district of Odisha's tribal people depend on agriculture, shifting cultivation, forest produce collection, and wage labour. Livelihoods are largely subsistence-oriented and vulnerable to natural and market fluctuations south-western part of Odisha's tribes.

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REFERENCES :

1. Ali,A: Health Problem of the tribal communities. In Mohanti, k.k : Readings on tribal women and socio-economic Development. Tribal and harijan research-trining centre.
2. Bage , Mery Gabriela: Tribal Knowledge System : Studies on the Kharia and Kisan Tribes of Odisha.
3. Bairathi, S : Tribal culture, economy and Health. New Delhi, Rawat.
4. Bhoi, Jagadisha Chandra: Gond janajatira samaja o sanskruti,agraduta,bankabazar, cuttack odisha, 2020, (odia).
5. Bhol, Lata: Ho Parampara o gyanakosa , academy of tribal dialects and culture,bbsr ,(odia).
6. Das Patnaik, PS and Das Sarat.: 1976 a comparative analysis of the Cognitive abilities of unschooled children of Bondaa and Dongria Kandha of Koraput district, Adibasi, Life in sonabeda plapeau, tribal and horijan research-cum traning institute Bhubaneswar, 1984
7. Mohanty, B.B, Mohanty, S.C: 2009, Tribal customs and traditions: An Anthropological study of bonda, kutia kandha & lanjia saora tribes of odisha , volume-1
8. Pradhan, Ranjan, paraja jibana o sanskruti, Paschima publication, BBSR Odisha, 2007 (odia)
9. Rout, Siba Prasad: Social organization of the Bhunjias of Kalahandi Adibasi.

